

Using CRISPR/Cas9 to investigate the developmental roles of *Fcho*, *Pgm3*, and *Nckap1* in *Ciona*, Part 3: testing their roles in tail morphogenesis

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Introduction

We have been investigating three genes of interest in the non-vertebrate chordate *Ciona robusta*: *Fcho* (*FCH* and *mu* domain-containing endocytic adaptor), *Pgm3* (*Phosphoacetylglucosamine mutase 3*) and *Nckap1* (*NCK-associated protein 1*) and their roles in the development of the notochord, the defining feature of the chordate phylum. These genes were identified as notochord-expressed orthologs of human disease-associated genes by Arcadia Science's Zoogle platform [1, 2]. Previously, we designed and validated CRISPR single-chain guide RNAs (sgRNAs) targeting these genes [3]. Later, we investigated their involvement in early notochord cell intercalation and convergent extension [4]. Although no reproducible, significant notochord intercalation defects were uncovered during early embryogenesis upon knocking out these genes in the cells that give rise to the notochord, we then decided to look at the resulting CRISPR larvae at the end of embryogenesis. While notochord cell elongation begins at the initial tailbud stage (~7.5 hours post-fertilization at 20°C), notochord morphogenesis continues through the hatching larval stage (~17 hours post-fertilization at 20°C). Starting from the end of intercalation (**Figure 1**), additional steps of elongation, vacuolization, and tubulogenesis transforms the notochord into an extracellular fluid-filled tube that serves as a hydrostatic skeleton for the swimming *Ciona* larvae [5]. Here we describe our latest milestone in this project, sharing our preliminary results obtained while knocking out these genes again but now assaying the morphology of the notochord and overall surrounding tail in hatched larvae.

Figure 1. Steps of *Ciona* notochord morphogenesis.

Schematic of notochord morphogenesis in *Ciona* embryos, beginning with notochord cell intercalation around the initial tailbud stage (Hotta Stage 17-18), through elongation and tubulogenesis, until the hatching/swimming larva stage (Hotta Stage 26).

Methods

To assess the potential role of these genes in notochord elongation and tubulogenesis, we performed tissue-specific CRISPR/Cas9-mediated mutagenesis early *Ciona* F0 embryos [6]. We used the dechorionation and electroporation protocol previously described by Christiaen et al. [7, 8]. Synchronized zygotes were electroporated with gene-specific combinations of plasmids encoding the sgRNAs described in **Table 1**, together with the *Foxa.a>Cas9::Geminin^{N-terminus}* plasmid to induce mutations early in early *Foxa.a+* cell lineages as previously described [4, 9]. *Foxa.a* is expressed in several cells giving rise to multiple tissues, including the notochord and endoderm [10]. The latter tissue is of note, as *Pgm3* was shown to be upregulated in notochord and endoderm at the early tailbud stage, and sustained at least through late tailbud [11]. The *Brachyury>H2B::mCherry* reporter plasmid was also co-electroporated in order to label transfected notochord cells. A negative control experiment was performed using the same Cas9 and reporter plasmids together with a *U6>control* sgRNA plasmid targeting no *Ciona* sequence [12]. Per 700 μ l of electroporation volume, we used 80 μ g of sgRNA plasmid (40 μ g of each when combined), 35 μ g of Cas9 plasmid, and 20 μ g of *Brachyury>H2B::mCherry*.

Larvae were raised to 17.5 hpf at 20°C, fixed, stained with fluorescent phalloidin, and mounted on glass slides for microscopy. Larvae were imaged using a scanning point confocal microscope (Zeiss), as well as using an epifluorescence microscope (Leica) for scoring and tail length measurements. Confocal image Z-stacks were processed in Fiji/ImageJ, while tail measurements were performed in Leica LASX software. Tails lengths were measured roughly along the anterior-posterior axis, and larvae were also qualitatively scored for wild-type or truncated tails.

Gene targeted	sgRNAs used	Mutation efficacy (indel rate)
<i>Pgm3</i>	Pgm3.1.83	23%
	Pgm3.2.27	>12.5%
<i>Fcho</i>	Fcho.1.34	43%
	Fcho.5.112	>15%
<i>Nckap1</i>	Nckap1.2.74	>15%
	Nckap1.8.103	>15%

Table 1. Selected sgRNAs used in this study.

Our sgRNA combinations used in CRISPR/Cas9 experiments and their estimated efficacies based on indel frequencies in sequenced target amplicons, from Johnson et al. 2025. An exact efficacy rate was not ascertained when amplicons spanned natural SNPs or indels (Pgm3.2.27, Fcho.5.112, Nckap1.2.74, and Nckap1.8.103). Instead, an efficacy “floor” was given, as efficacy was at least higher than the largest CRISPR-induced indel peak measured.

Results

When compared to negative control larvae, *Pgm3* CRISPR and *Fcho* CRISPR larvae had visibly shortened, truncated tails. In contrast, *Nckap1* CRISPR larvae tails did not appear to be significantly different from that of negative control larvae. This was observed both through measurements of individual tail lengths (**Figure 2A**), as well as qualitative assessment of tails that appeared truncated (**Figure 2B**). Notochord cells were still arrayed more or less linearly in

Pgm3 and *Fcho* CRISPR larvae, suggesting that earlier intercalation was not affected as much as later processes of notochord cell or lumen elongation, and/or elongation of surrounding tissues such as tail muscles or endodermal strand (**Figure 3**). *Pgm3* CRISPR appeared to have the largest effect, as the reduction in tail length was most pronounced in this condition, though qualitatively both *Pgm3* and *Fcho* CRISPR conditions were comparable as far as frequency of tail elongation defects (**Figure 2B**).

Figure 2: Effect of *Pgm3*/*Nckap1*/*Fcho* CRISPR on tail elongation.

A) Plot showing tail measurements of individual larvae. $n = 40$ for each condition. Statistical analysis was performed as ordinary one-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparison tests. ****: $p < 0.0001$, *: $p = 0.0324$, ns: $p = 0.0789$. B) Plot showing scoring same larvae as in panel A, for normal/wild type tails and for truncated tails. $n = 40$ for each condition. Fisher's Exact Test was performed comparing each CRISPR condition to the negative control. ****: $p < 0.0001$, *: $p = 0.0016$, ns: $p = 0.4391$. Only larvae expressing *Brachyury*>*H2B::mCherry* were imaged/scored.

Figure 3: *Pgm3* CRISPR larvae.

Representative confocal image slices of *Pgm3* CRISPR larvae of varying phenotype severity. Inset: notochord cells have intercalated but cell elongation and vacuole/lumen expansion is blocked. In green is AlexaFluor-647::phalloidin.

Conclusions and future plans

Overall, these suggest the *Pgm3* and *Fcho* might be required for tail elongation during *Ciona* embryogenesis, while *Nckap1* appears mostly dispensable (pending biological replicates). Our findings do not rule out a role for *Nckap1* in other developmental processes not assayed here, or in *Foxa.a*-negative tissues. The more pronounced effect of *Pgm3* CRISPR relative to *Fcho* CRISPR could be due to one or multiple factors, regardless of the gene products' biological functions. *Pgm3* is the more highly and widely expressed gene according to single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNAseq) data [2], and is upregulated in the endoderm and notochord during tail elongation according to mRNA *in situ* hybridization [11]. While the expression pattern of *Fcho* has yet to be determined by *in situ*, by either scRNAseq or bulk RNA sequencing its expression appears lower and relatively sparse [2]. Therefore, *Pgm3* might be rate-limiting in more cells crucial for tail morphogenesis in *Ciona*.

Our future plans are focused on *Pgm3*, on account of its higher expression levels and more robust knockout phenotype. Our next step is to determine the tissue-specific requirements for *Pgm3*. We will knock out *Pgm3* only in the endoderm or the notochord and assay tail elongation. It is possible that the severe defect we describe here might be due primarily to disrupting *Pgm3* in the endoderm, or in the notochord, for instance. To do this we can use endoderm- or notochord-specific promoters to drive Cas9 expression in only one tissue at a time.

We also plan on investigating the mechanism of *Pgm3* in tail elongation. In mammals, *Pgm3* is vital for protein glycosylation. Previous work has shown that protein glycosylation is required for proper notochord lumen expansion in *Ciona* [13]. We hypothesize that *Pgm3* in the endoderm and/or notochord may be required for glycosylation of extracellular matrix and/or cell surface receptors involved in tail elongation and lumen expansion. Proteomic analysis of *Pgm3* CRISPR larvae might reveal such downstream glycoproteins.

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